

Site: SPHINX TEMPLE Season GS 79-80

Area: N COLONNADE Square R16 Locus Number (4d)

26/II/80: R16A1

Progress of Excavation Mud Spots Large limestone Frags, some

granite shows on surface, Matrix looks more gypsumy-mottled
Many large frags - down to surface of (5)-(6). Shards seemed
to pick up more toward N Balk surface (5)-(6) which slopes
down in depression to N. (4d) Removed w/ trowel tip. At
lower surface of (5)-(6) near R16A1 N Balk (4d) contained
several frags spots of 1. Pinkish mortar some coated w/ red material;
2. Greyish-buff gypsum some w/ many small alabaster particles
or inclusions in matrix. // 3/II/80 R16A2: Surface shows less stone frags than ->

Locus Description "MOTTLED GREY SAND GYPSUM MIX" w/ grey mud inclusions

Location in Square _____

Under Locus (4c) BROWN SAND W. STONE RUBBLE Over Locus (5)-(6)

Locus Dimensions 8.00 - 7.86 surface

Levels _____

Analysis of non-artifactual materials LARGE TO FINE limestone frags,
Many granite, alabaster, some dolerite chips, frags. Grey buff
purer gypsum inclusion spot near R16 N Balk E side. Mortar
(pink speckled or white) frags. Many mud spots and finer flecks
of mud in matrix. More shards than other loci, 2 remotely
diagnostic (1 CRW conical bottom, one upper partial rim w/ inflection)
Carbon flecks throughout interspersed. 1 large charcoal frag.
consolidated w/ wax.

R16A, but still mud spots, average elevation same, directly under large stone level at bottom (4c). Large limestone boulder showing in (4c) at NE corner trench embedded in (4d). (See plans). // Cleared to surface (4e) arbitrary since (4c) looks here to be merely continuation of (4d). Large boulder in NE corner rests on other large limestone pieces almost as big. Fill contained several diaphanous sherds, 1 large sherd CW broad mold-type () 1 large chert frag (looks artificially split). Some small bone chips - these maybe contamination or came from part of deposit met by clean (mod?) sand at W. Balk.